

DairyPPENet: A dataset for detection of hygiene-related personal protective equipment in dairy processing plants

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Abstract

This article introduces DairyPPENet, a dataset designed for detecting hygiene-related personal protective equipment (PPE) used in dairy processing environments.

The dataset was collected from CCTV cameras installed in a dairy processing plant located in Valdivia, Chile. Images were extracted from RTSP video streams and manually annotated using the CVAT annotation platform.

DairyPPENet contains 751 RGB images and 6,692 annotated PPE instances belonging to three classes relevant for food safety: **mask**, **hairnet**, and **glove**.

The dataset reflects real industrial conditions including partial occlusions, worker posture variability, multi-person scenes, and small object detection challenges.

Image filenames encode the original capture timestamp, allowing temporal traceability of frames extracted from video streams.

The dataset is publicly available through IEEE DataPort and can be used for training and benchmarking object detection models in food safety monitoring systems.

Keywords: computer vision; object detection; personal protective equipment; food safety; industrial dataset

Specifications Table

Subject area	Computer Vision / Food Safety
Specific subject area	Detection of hygiene PPE in dairy plants
Type of data	RGB images and bounding box annotations
How data were acquired	Frames extracted from RTSP CCTV streams
Data format	JPG images and YOLO annotation files
Number of images	751
Training images	649
Validation images	102
Number of annotated instances	6692
Classes	mask, hairnet, glove
Data source location	Valdivia, Chile
Data accessibility	IEEE DataPort (https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/e6r7-1q71)

Value of the Data

- The dataset focuses on hygiene-related PPE used in food production environments.
- It contains real industrial scenes captured from CCTV monitoring systems.

- It includes small objects such as gloves, which are challenging for object detection models.
- The dataset can support research on automated compliance monitoring systems in food processing plants.
- It enables benchmarking of deep learning models for industrial computer vision applications.

1 Background

Food safety regulations require workers in dairy processing facilities to wear specific personal protective equipment (PPE) such as masks, hairnets and gloves to prevent contamination during food handling. Workers themselves may constitute a relevant source of contamination during handling and processing operations in dairy environments [1].

Computer vision systems have been increasingly explored for automated monitoring of hygiene-related practices in food handling and food safety control [2, 3]. In parallel, automated PPE compliance assessment has been studied in industrial environments using deep learning techniques [4].

However, most publicly available PPE datasets focus on construction, electrical or medical environments rather than food production contexts. To support research in food safety monitoring systems, DairyPPENet was developed as a dataset specifically focused on detecting hygiene-related PPE used in dairy processing plants.

2 Data Description

The dataset contains 751 images annotated with three PPE classes:

- mask
- hairnet
- glove

Images were extracted from RTSP streams recorded by CCTV cameras installed inside a dairy processing plant in Valdivia, Chile.

Because the cameras remain fixed in position and orientation, the main sources of variability in the dataset are associated with worker motion, posture changes, occlusions, and differences in object scale rather than large changes in the global scene configuration.

Annotations were generated using the CVAT annotation tool [5] and exported in YOLO object detection format [6].

2.1 Dataset summary

Attribute	Value
Total images	751
Total annotations	6692
Number of classes	3
Training images	649
Validation images	102
Annotation format	YOLO
Image format	JPG
Camera sources	2 CCTV cameras
Location	Dairy processing plant, Valdivia, Chile

2.2 Dataset structure

```
DairyPPENet/  
  images/  
    train/  
    val/  
  labels/  
    train/  
    val/  
  dataset.yaml
```

Each annotation file contains bounding boxes using normalized YOLO coordinates:

<class_id> <x_center> <y_center> <width> <height>

2.3 Example dataset images

Figure 1: Example images from the DairyPPENet dataset showing annotated PPE instances under real operational conditions, including posture variation, partial occlusions, and small-object challenges.

2.4 Bounding box spatial distribution

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of bounding box centers across the image space.

2.5 Object size distribution

Figure 3: Histogram of bounding box sizes in normalized image coordinates.

3 Experimental Design, Materials and Methods

3.1 Dataset acquisition workflow

Figure 4: Workflow used to generate the DairyPPENet dataset.

3.2 Data acquisition

Video streams were obtained from CCTV cameras installed inside a dairy processing plant. Frames were periodically extracted from RTSP streams to generate still images representing typical working conditions. The image filenames preserve the original capture timestamp, which enables temporal traceability of the extracted frames.

3.3 Annotation process

Images were manually annotated using the CVAT annotation platform [5]. Bounding boxes were drawn around each visible PPE element. Annotations were exported using the YOLO annotation format [6].

3.4 Dataset split

To evaluate model generalization across camera viewpoints, the dataset split was performed based on camera source:

- Camera A: training images
- Camera B: validation images

Both cameras were installed in the same processing room but provided different viewpoints of the production area.

3.5 Example dataset usage

A baseline experiment was performed using a YOLO-based detector to demonstrate potential dataset usage [6]. This example is intended only to illustrate how the dataset can be used for training object detection models in industrial food safety applications.

Training configuration:

- Model: YOLOv11n
- Input resolution: 960
- Training epochs: 150

4 Limitations

- The dataset was collected in a single dairy processing facility.
- Only three PPE classes are annotated.
- Gloves frequently appear as small objects and may be partially occluded.
- Worker posture and interaction with the environment can affect the visibility of PPE elements.
- The dataset includes only two camera viewpoints.

Future work may extend the dataset by including additional facilities, more diverse viewpoints and additional PPE categories.

Ethics Statement

Images were collected with authorization from the collaborating company. Eye-region blurring was applied to protect worker identity.

CRedit Author Statement

Mirko H. Gueregat: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Luis Veas Castillo: Supervision, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

Christian Lazo Ramirez: Supervision, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Data Availability Statement

The dataset supporting this study is publicly available at IEEE DataPort: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/e6r7-1q71>.

The dataset includes annotated images and labels in YOLO format.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

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